

Samaritan History, Fiction, and Bad Fantasy

by

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I. Indications of alteration of places in the work of A.F. for the worse

In the last pages of my article *The Second Recension of the Work of Abu 'l-Fateh* I argued that there were indications that what had been written by Abu 'l-Fateh (hereinafter A.F.) had been replaced in a few places. My evidence was that what was written there was inferior to the rest of A.F.'s work. Important information is left out, a lot of what is said is obviously not historical, there are internal contradictions showing the clumsy piling up of unrelated parts, and there is borrowing from Jewish stories. At the time I thought inferior material must have been substituted after the time of A.F. because there seemed to be no plausible explanation of how he could have not had access to reliable records for a few sets of events while having detailed accurate information for most events and sets of events. I now see that the question is harder than it seemed then, and two possible mechanisms have to be weighed up.

In my article I brought up the astonishing omission of most of what was important in the first century A.D. and the early second century, and the erroneous dating and characterisation of Bāba Rabba. I will now try to give a complete list of places where A.F. might have only had rubbish to work with, and had to pick out the least bad version. Or it might be that whoever replaced some passages with rubbish used the least bad version on hand. I have tried to put them in logical order as far as it could be done. There are not many.

The first place is the reign of Herod. Most of what is written there is taken from Jewish popularised history such as you can read in Rabbinic works. The overall bad picture of Herod does not agree with how Samaritans fared under his rule.

The second place is most of the first century and the first part of the second. Nearly everything is left out after Sejanus. Neither Jewish revolt is mentioned. There is only a mention of an attack on Jerusalem and destruction of the temple by Hadrian --- not Vespasian --- for no adequate reason. The Roman governors are not mentioned. Agrippas is not mentioned. The state visit of a Samaritan dignitary to Rome in the time of Claudius is not mentioned. (See my book of 2024, p. 48). Vespasian and Hadrian are fused. No reason is given for the combined Vespasian and Hadrian to come to Jewish or Samaritan territory. The improvement of the Samaritan sanctuary by Hadrian is not mentioned. (See my book of 2024, p. 13). The parts of the story are contradictory. The curse on Hadrian at the end does not fit the story, in which

¹ **The author has no connection with the State of Israel.**

relations with the Samaritans are good if a bit uneven. The unevenness seems to come from adding Jewish stories. The curse is the standard Jewish one on Hadrian.

The third place is the whole of what is said about Bāba Rabba. What follows is condensed and it is assumed that my article mentioned will be consulted for details. He is put too late, partly from confusion of the name of his father Nātānel and grandfather Iqbon with two later High Priests, but mainly because he has been turned into a resistance leader in the popular mind. A.F. tells us here that he took the detailed information about administration under B.R. from the Tūlāda. Or someone else says so. If from A.F., this sentence tells us the information was not in any histories known to him. This information about administration is incompatible with what he writes next about moderately successful resistance to Rome. The wrong dating is unexpected. The Tūlāda gives the date of death of B.R. as 4600 A.M., corresponding to after late 174 A.D. but before late 175 A.D. The date A.M. could easily have been converted to Seleucid years by A.F. See my article *Restoring the Traditional Linkage between Samaritan and Foreign Dating* and my book of 2024, p. 161 note 35. It is hard to imagine that A.F. didn't work it out. It is far more likely that someone else restored the information about administration and added the account of the legendary Bāba.

The fourth place where the content is confused and inadequate --- or better, just plain bad --- is the narrative of the Exile. It gets better towards the end. The exile of the northern kingdom and the southern kingdom are fused. Actually whoever thought it up does not know about the northern kingdom and the southern kingdom. He thinks only Samaritans lived in the north. He has not read the clear statement in the Arabic Joshua book and made by A.F., that some people in the north recognised the shrines set up by Jeroboam, and some recognised Shilo and Jerusalem. The Assyrians and Babylonians are fused. The narrator thinks the length of the exile of the northern kingdom was the same as for the southern kingdom, and takes the figure of seventy years from Jewish records. (Though it is quite possible that the Babylonians exiled some people from the former northern kingdom separately from what had been done by the Assyrians, this is not what is said here. The narrative is not detailed). The narrator thinks the whole of Samaria and the whole of the south were emptied of population. He says nothing about who lived north of Samaria. He has not heard of Assyrians or Babylonians and makes them vaguely Aramaean in the version in the extant manuscripts of A.F., or Persians in the version in the Arabic Joshua book. He has not heard of Assyria or Babylonia and says the exiles were sent to all parts of the world. In the version in the manuscripts of A.F., he does not know how this rule by Aramaeans turns into rule by Persians. He does not know the name of the Persian emperor responsible for ending the exile.

The fifth unsatisfactory bit, pure fiction this time, is the narrative of how a High Priest's daughter was framed by two men and executed by her father, after which it was decided to use **normal** caution in examining witnesses. I say this is stupid fiction because it assumes there was no proper procedure for examining witnesses till someone came across a crude method by accident, and assumes that the accused is not represented in court, and assumes that a judge could hear a case personally relevant to him, and assumes that there was no council and the High Priest had sole absolute authority. This could only have been written when Samaritans

had no power to try legal cases beyond strict limits. It is the same stupid fiction as in the well-known chapter in the long version of the book of Daniel. A.F. or someone else does his best with it by saying at the start that the story shows how the High Priest was always too hasty and too harsh.

The sixth unsatisfactory bit is the narrative of some supposed exile to all parts of the world followed by return in the late Persian period. See my book of 2024, p. 24, for an explanation of how this can be explained as overdone hysterical Hellenistic fiction. (Though we can all think of worse). It might be true that some people moved to Samaritan territory in Bashan. It is more likely that the author (not A.F.) thought there must have been an exile. This story is based on true reminiscence of the imaginatively named Simon the Just and what might be true reminiscence of interruption of use of the Samaritan sanctuary. It is combined with what might be a true record of control of Samaria by Jewish governors at the end of the Persian period perhaps with interruption of use of the Samaritan sanctuary. If you read carefully it does not say this Simon was appointed by the Persians, and he is called a king. The meaninglessly named Simon the Just did have the power of a king without the title.

The seventh piece of weak fiction is at the start of the second notice of the Dositheans, where it is said that Dositheos was a Jew, and he was commissioned by the Jewish Sanhedrin to cause damage by leading Samaritans astray. This is immediately contradicted by saying he was son of the Samaritan High Priest. The story of how the High Priest sought to have him captured and the seven men sent out were overcome by nefarious magic powers when they immersed themselves in a pool with a spell on it would have been entertaining in its day. (It's hard to find adjectives for all the different kinds of rubbish as you get further down the list).

The eighth piece of stupid fiction is the story about a magician called Simon between the second and third notices of the Dositheans. This figure is a debased form of the Simon the Samaritan invented by the Christian Church, debased from the form it has in the Clementine book and some related apocryphal writings about Peter. The datum about the location of Stephen's house is a give-away. The bit about the advice to Simon by Philo the Jew not to wipe out Christianity because he would be working against God can only be Christian. (How was it thought he could manage to do it if it would be working against God?). It is inspired by a passage in the book of Acts with words supposedly coming from a Jew, but this time with inferior wording.

The ninth dubious story is the substitution of two rats for two pigeons intended for sacrifice in the Jerusalem temple by two Samaritans improbably named Ephraim and Menasseh. The story is not stupid, whether fiction or not. It is not fiction in the usual sense. There really were Jewish stories saying Samaritans had done this. It is true that a lot of Samaritans would have liked to do this, and would have thought it funny if it happened. I would be highly amused myself. That does not mean it ever happened. How would the Jew going to Jerusalem not see the rats when he went to feed the pigeons? Why would anyone take pigeons to Jerusalem instead of buying them on the spot? This story might not come from the collection of fiction or fictionalised history. Against this supposition is that it comes between the story

about the High Priest's daughter and the one about Hadrian. It seems that either A.F. copied these three stories as a block, or someone substituted them as a block. Between the three of them they replace everything from Tiberius and Sejanus to Antoninus (who is a fusion of Antoninus Pius and Marcus Aurelius).

The tenth unsatisfactory narrative is what is said about Alexander. The narrative is not stupid, but it is not history either. There is a kernel of history in the claim that Alexander recognised the face of the High Priest, in that he did ask to be blessed by Mt. Gerizim and did make an unconditional irrevocable endowment. This important datum is left out and only known from a casual mention in another place, showing that whoever wrote this was not trying to record history. It is obviously true that Alexander must have recognised the status of the High Priest. See my book of 2024, pp. 108 bottom to 109 top. All the same, the claim that he recognised the face of the High Priest is not history. It is not history either that all males born over the next year were called Alexander, though it is entirely plausible that it was explained to Alexander why no statues could be set up. There is an exact Jewish equivalent to both stories. Neither version of the pair of stories has primacy. Neither is history.

The eleventh stupid narrative is the long tedious simple-minded Shobak story set in the time of Joshua. This story is incompatible with the concept of the Time of Favour and the purpose of the Arabic Joshua book. More will be said about clumsy damage to this book further on. It is not certain that this story was known to A.F. It could have been interpolated. For the purpose of this article there is no need to go into this question.

We need not count the last two stories about Bāba Rabba, since A.F. or perhaps someone else says he does not believe them. The one about Bāba's nephew going to Constantinople and becoming a high official without anyone knowing he is a Samaritan is well written but you can't make a silk purse out of a sow's ear. The next one about Bāba tricking the Romans into thinking he has an army of dead soldiers ready to fight is too inane for me to bear to describe.

II. A couple of less obvious examples

These are the only bad or stupid or dubious passages in the book. (The one about Alexander is not objectionable or stupid but it obscures an important event that did happen and which says a lot about Alexander's policy. The one about substitution of two rats is not history but accurately gives the date when the Jewish officials decided to formally split Israelite religion into two separate religions). It is too much for coincidence that the second, third, fourth, fifth, sixth and tenth have equivalents in the additions to the Arabic Joshua book. (The chapter about Hadrian is in the manuscript used by Juynboll but not any other manuscript known to me. The chapter about the High Priest's daughter is not in the manuscript used by Juynboll but is in every other manuscript known to me). Besides this, an introduction to the story about Bāba's nephew is there as well, again too much for coincidence. There are two possible conclusions. One is that A.F. knew of a book closely resembling the present form of the Arabic Joshua book with the pseudo-historical additions, though not identical with it. He used this out of necessity, because all authentic records had been lost. The other possible

conclusion is that someone systematically went through the book and inserted all the pseudo-historical episodes. What was written by A.F. was removed, to make room and save effort in copying, and to avoid contradiction.

What is in the book by A.F. as we have it now is a superior version of the rubbish. In the form of the Arabic Joshua book in our hands it says the exile was at the hands of the Persians. Someone thought that if it was the Persian emperor that ended the exile it must have been Persians that started it. In the book by A.F. there is something that can be understood as Aramaeans. In the form of the Arabic Joshua book in our hands it says Bāba was the eldest of three sons. In the extant manuscripts of the book by A.F. it says he was youngest. This takes care of an anomaly in dating. It was said that Bāba is put too late, in the time of Alexander Severus. This makes too many years between the accession of his father to office and the start of his activity, if he was the eldest son. The story is still fiction. The long version of the story about Bāba's nephew known to A.F. is better written than the crude version in the Arabic Joshua book as known to us. That only means the author poured eucalyptus oil over a pile of horse droppings to scent it. The capital of the empire is Constantinople. The nephew drops his Roman disguise after the first part of the story and all of a sudden can inexplicably command military force. Drenching with eucalyptus oil is not the answer. What you get is artificial koala wee.

Seven out of the eleven unsatisfactory or partly unhistorical places in the book by A.F. as we have it are due to relying on something close to the extant form of the Arabic Joshua book. It is eight out of twelve if you count the stories about Bāba that A.F. or someone else says he does not believe. Every single one of the seven extant pseudo-historical additions to the Arabic Joshua book has been copied into the extant manuscripts of the work of A.F. The obvious question is whether there was a form of the Arabic Joshua book with historical appendixes, as now known, or a separate collection of historical episodes. In favour of the second explanation is that not all the unsatisfactory passages are in the extant manuscripts of this book. Every single one of the seven pseudo-historical pieces attached to the extant manuscripts of the Arabic Joshua book is bad. They all come from the same place.

III. Damage to the Arabic Joshua book

The Arabic Joshua book has not been treated well. As I observed in the Bibliography to my book of 2024, every manuscript bristles with errors, though fortunately some of the errors are different from one manuscript to another. Some errors are corrected by A.F., but he could not do most of what was needed. The forms of the names of the Kings of the Time of Favour could not be restored with the knowledge and method of his time, for example. ² The damage

² It has been asserted without evidence and against the evidence that the content of this book has been lifted from the Greek translation. Decisive evidence against this is that the equivalent of the Masoretic form Yiftaḥ has the correct final letter. It has been asserted without evidence and against evidence that the names are taken from the Hebrew of the corresponding Jewish book. The obvious answer to that is that there are authentic dialect differences. For example, instead of the Masoretic Shimshon the Samaritan has the form Shumshom. Another answer is that there are differences of form going beyond dialect differences. For the Masoretic Baraq the Samaritan has Faraq. A proof that there

extends to content. It can be seen that there were originally terse notes on each King. There are some preserved by A.F. that are not in the extant manuscripts, but the opposite is true as well. One sentence about Samson is in the right place and another is in the next chapter. Most of the notes are lost altogether. I would not like to say whether any content about Joshua has been lost, but my impression on careful reading is that none has been lost. See my article mentioned in the footnote. Beyond corruption in single places and some loss of content, someone got it into their head to insert the long dreary Shobak story. My reaction to this needs explanation. Aside from being dreary and silly, this story denies the basic premise of the book, that conditions were perfect in the Time of Favour, you might say by definition. I have argued that the book in its present form but without this hamhanded insertion was composed to assert that the present era is unsatisfactory and that there was once a Time of Favour, to explain how the Time of Favour was ended because people had shown they did not deserve it or want it, with an unspoken but clear explanation of how it can be brought back. I have argued that the book was composed to be acceptable to both the Dositheans and Sebuaeans to give them a formulation they could both accept, as a major necessary step in enabling them to work together. I have suggested a few times that there was an original very short book confirming that the commands of Deuteronomy had been carried out and that the promise of entry into Canaan and peace and prosperity connected with observance of the Torah had happened. Much later, in the process of accommodation between the two sects the record of the end of the Time of Favour was greatly elaborated. Whoever put the Shobak story in was clueless about the purpose of the book. This means the damage must have been done after both parties had agreed on formulation of this basic doctrine. There is evidence of good relations between the two parties in the Kitāb al-Kāfi, written in 1030 A.D., centuries before the definitive amalgamation. In my article *Samaritan Worship on the Meadow in the Time of Straying* I sum up indications that the long process reached final definitive amalgamation not long before 1300 A.D. In this connection I repeat the observation near the end of my article *The Second Recension* that whoever wrote the overdone wails of woe at the end of the second notice and third notice of the Dositheans about undefined harm they had brought about knew nothing whatsoever about them and was waffling.

Once the Joshua book had stopped being needed as an official statement agreed on by both parties, it would easily have suffered from careless copying, and this accounts for the mistakes everywhere. Once the purpose had been forgotten and it was seen as only a historical record, an invitation to add to it at the start and at the end and in the middle was seen. There are additions at the start. Not all of them are related to Joshua. There are two different versions of a set of additions at the start in different manuscripts, one longer than the other. The manuscript used by Juynboll has the short version. The pieces at the start are as unedifying and useless as the Shobak story or the additions at the end. It needs to be asked why every single one of the additions at the end is bad. You could say that they are what you would expect to

was no borrowing from any Jewish book is that the names of the three before Samson are in opposite order in the Samaritan. See part 4 of my article *The Transmission of the Samaritan Joshua-Judges*. It is normal in allegedly academic writing on the Samaritans to make assertions without evidence or while concealing evidence. It is normal to quote such assertions as data and use them in argument, using the unspoken assertion that if someone has said something it must be true.

appeal to the people that attached the additions at the start. That does not mean all the additions at the end are entirely useless. The piece about Hadrian has the true datum that he set up a temple on the lower peak and appointed Samaritans as guards. The inferior form in the Arabic Joshua book has the useful datum that the temple was dedicated to Serapis, though the statement in its present form shows misunderstanding. See my book of 2024, p. 16 and p. 19. The piece about circumstances leading up to the appearance of the fictitious version of Bāba Rabba correctly defines the policy of three emperors. The description of the violence is greatly overdone under the influence of the frightful persecution under Christian rule, but if you read carefully you can see details about policy. The statement that Commodus did not originate the policy of repression, but did what the Senate or powerful figures wanted, fits what is known of him. The information that although Septimius Severus put heavy restrictions on Israelite religious observance and study, he did not force a pretence of worship of the Roman gods, is in character. He would not have allowed their dishonouring by sham worship. The information about repression of religious observance under these three emperors must be regarded as accurate history, provided it is borne in mind that the violence and murderousness depicted fits the later Christian emperors obeying the instructions of the Christian Church. It is entirely possible that the Samaritan leader was honoured by Philip and Otilia. He might well have been invited to make a state visit to Rome. The piece about the exile is bad at the start, but it has some true information near the end, though it is not detailed and not new. The bit about the High Priest's daughter is low quality fiction from start to finish, though not as bad as the story about Bāba's nephew.

It still needs to be asked whether the chapters in the manuscripts of the Arabic Joshua book are taken from a bigger collection. The unbelievable overstatement in the extant manuscripts of the work of A.F. that people fled to all parts of the world goes with the statement on the same level that the first exile was to all parts of the world. The Hellenistic over-composition in both places goes with the bit about the circumstances of the time of Bāba. The collection must have been longer than what we have, whether it was at the end of the Arabic Joshua book or a separate booklet.

IV. Consequences for use of the book by A.F. as a historical record

Now we come to an important question. Did A.F., who was thorough and had good critical sense, copy episodes that were rubbish, or a mixture of rubbish and fact? Why does he leave out everything between Sejanus and Hadrian? One possible answer is that he could not do otherwise. The collection of rubbish had become popular and no accurate records of some events and periods survived. This is still hard to believe. It is still hard to imagine that there were no accurate records of the exile, or the events of the first century A.D. and early second century, or the real position and date of Bāba Rabba, even if they were not commonly read. On the other hand A.F. or someone says he got his information about administration under Bāba from the Tūlāda, not a history. It will be argued that it is the final editor that says this. We might not have the whole book as it left the hands of the author. Someone might have thought he could improve it by SYSTEMATICALLY replacing sections with episodes from the inferior collection. In favour of this proposal it could be pointed out that what is said about Jesus in the

story about Simon the magician in between the second and third notices of the Dositheans partly contradicts what was said by A.F. about Jesus earlier on. It remains improbable that anyone would have inserted stories or replaced stories. There it is. There is the phenomenon, and there are only two possible explanations (unless both happened). Argument will be given that passages were replaced. At first glance this sounds implausible, but it will be shown how it could have happened.

There are some important conclusions about method from all this, whichever of the two explanations of the deficiencies in the places listed is right, or if both are partly right. One is that the work of Khidr in the Comprehensive History and the unique readings of ms. A in these places must be looked at systematically. A good example of valuable information from the work of Khidr is given in my book of 2024, pp. 116 middle to 117 middle. The other conclusion is that there is no reason to doubt information from outside about these events or periods because it is not in the extant manuscripts of the work of A.F. No-one hesitates to prefer the account of the exile of some of the inhabitants of the northern kingdom in the Jewish scriptures over the account in the extant manuscripts of A.F. In the same way, no-one doubts the existence of Agrippas, or that there were two Jewish revolts. It follows that there is no justification for doubting that there was a massacre of Samaritans by Pilate or in his time, though the version given by Josephus is suspect. There is no justification for doubting the report of a state visit by a Samaritan dignitary to Rome in the time of Claudius by Justin of Neapolis. (Commonly called Justin Martyr, but Justin the Unsurprisingly Executed would be better). Justin does not call it a state visit, but that is what he describes. **There is no justification for doubting the date of death of Bāba Rabba in the Tūlāda, 174 / 175 A.D.**, regardless of the date of the start of his work as being in the time of Alexander Severus in the stories in the work of A.F. as we have it. **There is no justification for doubting his systematic administration as recorded in detail in the Tūlāda and copied into the book written by A.F.**, regardless of the stories about a moderately successful resistance leader known to A.F. or in our manuscripts of his work.

V. What the final editor meant by putting Dositheos where he did

Now we can work out why Dositheos is mentioned after Bāba Rabba in the book by A.F. as we have it. The short answer is that he is not put just after, as is commonly asserted without looking properly. He is put long after, as a signal to the reader. Now to explain.

Here is the material before and after the mention of Dositheos. We start with Augustus, who is clearly mentioned in the right place. 1. Augustus. 2. Jesus. His date of birth is said to be 1,300 years from the start of the Fānūta. A.F. puts entry into Canaan half-way through 2795 A.M. That means he makes the first year of the Fānūta 3055 A.M. Adding 1,299 [sic] gives 4354 A.M. So Jesus was born after completion of 4354 A.M. or during 4355 A.M. For A.F. year 1 A.D. started during 4427 A.M. and year 1 B.C. started during 4426 A.M. That means he puts the birth of Jesus during 71 B.C. See my article *Restoring the Traditional Linkage*. I think someone has counted backwards from the wrong High Priest Nātānel. 3. Tiberius. 4. Sejanus. 5. The High Priest's daughter. 6. The substitution of two rats for two pigeons. So the Jerusalem temple is still standing. 7. Hadrian. 8. A fusion of Antoninus Pius and Marcus Aurelius. 9.

Claudius Ptolemaeus. 10. Alexander of Aphrodisias. 11. Commodus. 12. Septimius Severus. 13. Alexander Severus. 14. Bāba Rabba during the reign of an improbably long series of emperors starting with Alexander Severus. 15. Dositheos. 16. Simon the magician. Philo of Alexandria. Jesus. Apostles of Jesus. 17. Forms of Dosithean religion. 18. A daughter of a High Priest. 19. The building of the great synagogue under the High Priest Iqbon.

Events 1 to 13 are in the right order. Events 15, 16, and 17 are in the right order. The double mention of Jesus with slight disagreement between the two shows there has been alteration of the original order from event 4 to event 17.

Here is what seems to have gone wrong. The original notices of Vespasian and Hadrian and the two Jewish revolts and the improvement of the Samaritan sanctuary by order of Hadrian have been replaced by the present fictionalised history of the combined Vespasian and Hadrian. That has broken the dating of the start of the work by Bāba in the time of Hadrian and its continuation under Antoninus Pius and Marcus Aurelius. Then Bāba has been made son of the wrong Nātānel. With substitution of the new story of Hadrian fused with Vespasian, the stories about the High Priest's daughter and the substitution of the rats replaced everything after Sejanus. The two Jewish revolts are forgotten. There is only mention of an attack on Jerusalem by Hadrian and destruction of the temple with no adequate reason. No reason is given for the combined Vespasian and Hadrian to come to Jerusalem. What was lost included the notice of Dositheos, the notice of Simon the magician, and the notice of later developments in the Dosithean party. At first sight, just after Sejanus might seem too late for the notice of Dositheos, but the notice extends into developments after he died. This substitution left the three notices separated from the course of events. They were not lost altogether but recorded separately somehow as a set. Someone had to work out where to put the three notices. They were put after records of emperors reigning long after the death of the legendary Bāba, as a signal. This will be explained. The fictionalised legends of Bāba extend to the reign of Philip, who died in 249. The last emperor listed before the notice of Dositheos is Constantios II, who died in 361.

It is commonly said that A.F. puts Dositheos in the time of Bāba, or in a variant, just after him. This is bad reading. The notice is after mention of Constantios II. (The form Ṭī'os in two of the St. Petersburg fragments is right). A.F. could not have thought this was the right date, and neither could a restorer later on. No-one could have thought that before modern times and the end of systematic use of complete data and loss of critical thinking in writing about Samaritans. After the notice of Dositheos there is a notice of Simon the magician, Philo of Alexandria, and the first Christian apostles. Any restorer would have known Jesus did not live in the fourth century A.D. So would anyone before modern times and cognitive dissonance whenever writing about Samaritans. The scholion to the Tūlāda saying Dositheos appeared soon after Bāba can be ignored. It is not part of the book. It comes from bad reading of A.F.

In my article *The Second Recension* I pointed out on p. 9 and pp. 15 and 16 that there were indications of editing by someone other than A.F. in the notice about Dositheos and the one about Dosithean factions. The wails of woe about nothing that ever happened at the end of the second and third notices of the Dositheans, items 15 and 17 in the list on pp. 8 and 9, don't

fit A.F., who did not write verbiage. The statement at the end of the second notice, item 15, saying rules made up by one faction were laid down by Dositheos, is false and comes from carelessness or not knowing how to read properly. It could not have been written by A.F. The sentence about seven men that fled to Nawa is in the wrong place and the right place can't be found in the present state of the text of the notice. The information about factions, item 17 on the list, does not start intelligibly. There is a reference to seven men that either killed Dositheos, as in the manuscripts of the first recension, or became disciples of his, as in the second recension, having perished. As the text stands, there is no mention of seven such men before this, whichever of the two readings is accepted. There were seven men that accepted the status of Dositheos after immersing themselves, but they settled in one place and attracted followers, so it did not matter when they died. The three notices in their present form could not have come straight from the hand of A.F. They must have been clumsily touched up after being removed. This explains the slight disagreement between what is said about Jesus and his disciples in item 16 on the list and what is written in the extant manuscripts of A.F. after the notice of Herod.

The person that says he found the detailed description of administration under Bāba in the Tūlāda would be the person that restored the three notices, items 15, 16, and 17 on the list. He could not put the three notices back where they belonged. It would not have been enough to put them in without a little bit of editing. There would have been two notices of Jesus. There would have been slight disagreement between them. It would not be satisfactory to have two entries mostly duplicating each other, or two entries slightly disagreeing with each other. He would not have felt competent to harmonise and combine the two notices of Jesus or authorised to change anything. The dating by Jesus and Philo of Alexandria was obviously enough to tell everyone the place of the three notices was only provisional. Or was enough before modern times and purposeful cognitive dissonance. **The restorer hammers the message about the date home by going against the scholion to the Tūlāda and not putting Dositheos soon after Bāba but after Constantios II, a good hundred years later than that.** He could never have dreamt writers in the twentieth and twenty-first century would miss the message about the date driven in with a sledgehammer. He could not have foreseen the appearance of writers separating Dositheos from the Dositheans by making arguments from Arabic morphology without knowing Arabic. He could not have foreseen a string of authors declining to read what is written about the Dositheans honouring Sakte, a follower of Dositheos. He could never have imagined that in the twentieth and twenty-first century the date would be misread as the third century by a string of writers, while another string would say that although A.F. put Dositheos in the late fourth century well over a hundred years after the death of the legendary Bāba, what he meant was that he appeared in the time of Bāba. He could never have imagined that in the twentieth and twenty-first century a string of writers would say there had been two Samaritan Dositheoses, one in the early first century well known to Christian authors but unknown to A.F., and one in the late fourth century known to A.F. but unknown to anyone else, and both had done the same things. Mit der Dummheit kämpfen Götter selbst vergebens.

Instead of doing some editorial criticism and source criticism, effort has been wasted on trying to separate the person called Dositheos in the second and third notices of the Dositheans from the Dositheans in the first notice. Straight falsehoods about Arabic

morphology have been uttered. These were not deliberate lies, but came from wilful ignorance combined with arrogance. Not any better. Quite a few modern authors have denied any connection between the people called the Dustān and the person called Dusis. No-one with a real knowledge of Arabic has ever done this. I went into this kind of ignorance and arrogance in my book of 2024, pp. 98 to 101 middle. I pointed out that Dustān is a plural noun. Vilmar thought this was obvious. So did Appel. Anyone not knowing how to form noun plurals in Arabic is not qualified to make a pronouncement. Doing so is arrogance. Foolishness as well. Montgomery did it first, thinking he knew better than Vilmar, but plenty of others have done the same. In that place I pointed out that not one of the authors denying any connection between the people called the Dustān and the person Dusis had taken notice of the sentence in the third notice, item 17 on the list, saying that the Dustān (with plural verbs) honoured Sakte, who declared himself a follower of Dusis. This trick is used by Gaster, Bowman, Isser, Stenhouse, Crown, and Pummer. **If you don't take notice of the data that don't suit you you can prove anything.** Now to one last statement of common knowledge ignored by the kind of writers mentioned. Scribal error turning < stys > or < sts > into < sys > is easy in Arabic script. What is written < dwsys > in the extant manuscripts of A.F. must have originally been < dwstys > or < dwsts >, to be pronounced Dostis. In Hebrew script this error won't occur. **In the Tūlāda the name is written < dwsts > in Hebrew letters, to be pronounced Dostes.** The writers mentioned consistently ignore this datum. It is disgraceful that there is a need to explain how plurals are formed in Arabic to people that make statements about Arabic, or a need to tell people that make statements about Arabic about what can happen in Arabic handwriting, or a need to tell people to go and read the evidence of the form of the name in the Tūlāda. In modern writing on the Samaritans the standards of Wissenschaft are not followed. They are not known by some employees of universities and not respected by the rest.

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Some manuscripts. A pdf of ms. P of the book by Abu 'l-Fateḥ can be downloaded from my colleague Helen Gael's Profile page on Academia. A pdf of Z can be downloaded from the Digital Library of the Middle East here <https://dlmenetwork.org/library/catalog/aub-X893.7%20Ab9> A catalogue page with a link to the download page of C is here <https://archivesetmanuscrits.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cc102786m> There is a reproduction of D in Stenhouse's thesis.

A. С. Жамкочян, *Самаритянская Хроника Абу-л-Фатха из собрания Российской Национальной Библиотеки* (English title: *The Kitab at-Tarikh of Abu 'L-Fath (Samaritan Chronicle 1355 a.D. [sic])* Translated into Russian with Notes by Haroutun Jamgotchian). Moscow 1995. ISBN 5-7262-0203-1. The only competent translation into any language. A pdf can be downloaded from my colleague Helen Gael's Profile page on the Academia website. (But note that Vilmar's long detailed summary will do instead of a translation for some purposes). For political reasons this book is not listed in the survey of all aspects of Samaritan studies by Reinhard Pummer entitled *The Samaritans: A Profile*, published in

2016, though he knew of it. It shows up the incompetence of Stenhouse's translation into English. For the full disgraceful story see Part VII of my book of 2024.

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